

THE DIGITAL REGULATION COOPERATION FORUM

A RESEARCH NOTE ON
WORK IN PROGRESS

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Abstract

This paper introduces an evolving research engagement with the Digital Regulation Cooperation Forum (DRCF), based on a review of published outputs, 20 interviews and a roundtable discussion with senior DRCF staff. The DRCF was established in 2020 by the UK's Competition and Markets Authority (CMA), the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) and media and communications regulator Ofcom, with the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) joining in 2021. We trace the origins of the DRCF as a non-legislative initiative in the British tradition of concurrent regulation, offer a taxonomy of seven activities undertaken by the DRCF and interpret these activities from the perspective of the DRCF as a brokerage agent. We point to future challenges and opportunities for a flexible, risk-based and innovation-focused approach to digital regulation, especially in the context of AI.

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Introduction

The Digital Regulation Cooperation Forum was set up in 2020 by three public bodies with a key role in regulating the digital space. The initiating regulators were as follows: the Competition and Markets Authority (CMA), a designated national authority that seeks to promote competition, both within and outside the UK, for the benefit of consumers (this includes enforcing consumer protection legislation); the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO), the UK's independent regulator for Data Protection and Freedom of Information; and the Office of Communications (Ofcom), the UK media and communications regulator, regulating the TV, radio and video-on-demand sectors, with a key role in ensuring online safety. All these bodies have statutory status and exercise enforcement powers, reporting to the UK Parliament. A further statutory body, the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), the conduct regulator for financial services and markets, joined the forum in 2021. In what follows, these four bodies are referred to as the quartet.

We became interested in the DRCF when it was launched as this marked a decisive new step in the development of UK digital regulation, a topic on which we were already conducting research.² Its invention struck us as a welcome departure – an innovation working imaginatively with the grain of the UK's concurrent regulatory system.³ The DRCF was expressly designed to address the increased complexity, velocity, and interconnectedness of digital developments. On its inception, we speculated as to whether the DRCF might become a model, setting a template for adoption by other jurisdictions. Clearly, it has, as regulators elsewhere have followed suit.

This *Research Note* is our outsider's view of the DRCF. It is a first take, intended for discussion. We have deliberately kept it brief, minimising citations. This analysis draws on 20 interviews and a comprehensive survey of the DRCF's published outputs. An earlier version has been discussed with senior DRCF staff in a roundtable held under the Chatham House Rule on 7 March 2025.

² Kretschmer, M., Furgał, U., & Schlesinger, P. (2022). The Emergence of Platform Regulation in the UK: An Empirical-Legal Study. *Weizenbaum Journal of the Digital Society*, 4(1).

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34669/wi.wjds/2.2.4>.

³ Dunne, N. (2021). Concurrency. In B. Rodger, P. Whelan, & A. MacCulloch (Eds.), *The UK Competition Regime: A Twenty-year Retrospective* (pp. 255–281), Oxford University Press.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198868026.003.0010>

Regulatory innovation for our times

The DRCF's invention is a distinctive neo-regulatory response to fast-moving technological change and concentrations of economic power in the shape of Big Tech – which, depending on the specific platform in question, also may dispose of political, cultural and social heft. Although UK digital regulatory policy addresses national questions, British practice is inescapably connected to global developments.⁴

The start of 2025 marked a step-change in debate and position-taking over the scope of regulation and role of regulators in policy and political agendas, both nationally and internationally. Arguments for deregulation moved more decisively to centre-stage, deploying economic growth and innovation untrammelled by red tape as prime rallying calls. A background of intense systemic competition between the USA and the PRC is reshaping global geopolitics and geoeconomics. This is reinforcing the salience of national security in the digital sphere, spurring renewed advocacy of national industrial champions as agents of global competition in dependent economies, and in many liberal democracies, stimulating the use of defensive measures against disinformation. This *Research Note* was completed shortly after President Trump imposed US tariffs on global trading partners. The implications for digital regulation will doubtless be clearer as our research continues.

The UK's most recent phase of legislative activism in the digital space (notably, regarding competition, data, and online safety) put wind in the sails of digital regulators. However, we are rapidly shifting onto new ground. Facing a deregulatory moment, how will the DRCF's anchoring regulatory quartet – the CMA, ICO, FCA, and Ofcom – be affected, and how might this in turn play into the DRCF's future?

The DRCF's development

In its short life to date, the DRCF has successfully established itself as a UK cross-regulatory body that primarily addresses and interacts with some restricted publics, notably government departments, specialist parliamentary committees, non-DRCF regulators, cognate international regulators and associations, and a range of expert or interested stakeholders from industry, academia, and civil society. These are the DRCF's principal audiences and require diverse levels of effort and investment in relationship management.

⁴ Schlesinger, P. (2022). The Neo-regulation of Internet Platforms in the United Kingdom. *Policy & Internet*, 14(1). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/poi3.288>

The appointment of the first CEO in winter 2021 was key to the DRCF's strategic development. During Gill Whitehead's time in office, a DRCF website was established (signalling its distinctive relationship to the underpinning regulatory quartet), with output such as reports and workplans achieving greater visual impact and clearer brand identity. Recruitment of new talent, secondments, and enhancing the workforce's expertise came into stronger focus. Over time, this was accompanied by a steady uptick in face-to-face engagement along with occasional use of blogs and a range of engagements intended both to promote DRCF work and to solicit ideas.

Kate Jones became CEO in spring 2023. During her time in office, the linchpin role of mainly bilateral reports on specific regulatory issues has been repositioned: there is evidently more emphasis on wider-ranging engagement, notably in relation to government, parliament, industry, and consumer groups. In its approach to these various constituencies, the DRCF engages in policy *brokerage*, promoting its own analyses, offering guidance to industry players and civil society groups, and systematically gathering the intelligence required to stay at the cutting edge of technological change and policy development. The DRCF has developed key capacities for skilled intermediation. Its brokerage role across the field of regulatory activity and with the regulators' main publics is one of the DRCF's key strengths.

Brokerage types can be characterised by the direction of information flow and by the extent to which various actors are viewed as members of the same community. Building on our analysis of regulatory fields, several possible typologies of relations are conceivable. For example, DRCF activities may be seen as boundary spanning (keeping information flows between members tight) or boundary transgressing (working across looser federations of regulators, industry, society groups and policy) bringing agents in under specified conditions. For future strategic development at a time of uncertainty about the scope and shape of UK regulation, how boundary maintenance is pursued (by working both within and across jurisdictions) may be important for the DRCF's future.

The intensifying growth in establishing international relations with cognate regulators is notable. The DRCF's approach has been followed in Australia, Canada, the Irish Republic and the Netherlands modelled on the DRCF (those grouped as the INDRC⁵), along with steady promotion of UK convening power in the OECD, among European Union regulators, and those of other like-minded jurisdictions, as well as debate in international fora. The reweighted significance of broader engagement is signalled by the use of milestones.

⁵ The International Network for Digital Regulation Cooperation (INDRC) was launched in June 2023 and meets at regular intervals: <https://www.drcf.org.uk/projects/projects/international-network-for-digital-regulation-cooperation-indrc> (accessed 25 April 2025).

The DRCF's brokerage involves managing its boundary regime and regulatory know-how. Its claim to expertise is derived from the staff's bases in the regulatory quartet along with the cross-regulatory work reflected in its distinctive outputs. In our view, the DRCF may be characterised as a specialist cross-regulatory think tank that initially has built its reputation on the quality of its bilateral reports, subsequently adding less frequent but increasingly integrated trilateral and quadrilateral interventions to the mix. These may take the shape of formal coordination, such as joint statements on regulatory approaches. We are struck by the sustained pivotal role of bilateral collaborations for medium-term projects. The consistent line-up of investigatory and reporting partners is as follows: CMA/ICO, Ofcom/ICO, Ofcom/FCA, FCA/ICO. Over time, there has been a more confident use of the DRCF imprimatur on its investigations and reports. As part of its impact, the DRCF claims that it is shaping the direction of policy debate as a supplier of material used in brokerage. A shift to a three-year perspective on digital developments was announced in the 2024/25 annual plan, along with an emphasis on targeted horizon scanning. These commitments both shape and signal the think tank dimension's time horizons.

The DRCF's wider resonance may be judged from regular reviews and reports of its work published by legal and business consultants. It has been taken seriously as a model for quantum regulation by the Regulatory Horizons Council (an independent committee concerned with the implications of technological innovation that advises the UK government). That plaudit was cited by the DRCF as an instance of its impact. Its *national*/convening role is evident from the quarterly roundtables held with currently 13 UK non-DRCF regulators, as well as consultations focused on specific regulatory issues. When it evaluates its own impact, the DRCF refers to information gathered from its respondents, the *international* example it sets in regulatory coordination (endorsed by the OECD), and – as an indicator of its increased visibility – being referenced in some 160 open-source publications between 2020 and 2023. Its combined work, moreover, is endorsed by the member regulators as bringing greater efficiency to their own investigations.

For an outsider, there is evidence of the DRCF's growing profile and the sustained effort to extend its recognition as a distinctive player, as well as signalling the quartet's broad satisfaction with its performance. However, it remains genuinely difficult to know what the DRCF's overall impact on the wider policy arena might be. For instance, the DRCF's claim to have added value to the UK economy by way of cross-economy digital and AI regulatory policies is difficult to assess without calculating that value. However, the model of non-statutory coordination by a small team seems to be an effective and flexible response to a fast-changing technological environment.

A longer-term institutional strategy does not need to be underpinned by a statutory basis for the DRCF as a distinct body. Instead, it may build on the process obligations that already apply to the existing members of the quartet (such as information sharing, duties to consult, duties to cooperate): in practice, these sustain wider regulatory brokerage presently undertaken in the British tradition of concurrency.

The DRCF's status and functioning

The relationship between the DRCF and the regulatory quartet is set out in its Terms of Reference. Each member regulator operates according to its own legal constraints and has a distinctive organisational culture and practices while also being accountable for the delivery of its functions. The UK's concurrency framework for competition authorises information-sharing between the CMA and the other regulators. Secondment across regulators is also encouraged. The detailed 'working arrangements' are set out in the regulators' various Memoranda of Understanding. To date, this framework has enabled the quartet's autonomous bodies to pool effort, devise collaborative governance, and agree financial support for the DRCF.

Collectively, the quartet is the DRCF's *principal*. The regulators successively supply an annually rotating chair for the CEOs' quarterly meetings. The DRCF is the non-statutory *agent* of the member regulators, working within prescribed purposes and under well understood conditions. The resulting model of cross-regulator practice means that the DRCF's leadership must always be acutely conscious of how its relationship to the quartet is managed. The DRCF is keen to explain the scope and limits imposed by the Terms of Reference to its key publics. Although the DRCF is not itself established as a free-standing regulator, its activities constitute a distinctive flow of regulatory policy advice and coordination both to its principal and the other constituencies that it addresses.

Because the quartet's devolution of cross-regulatory cooperation to the DRCF has created a new entity, the forum's profile must be carefully double-branded: although the DRCF's logo has gradually acquired greater prominence in its outputs, a smaller-scale line-up of the member regulators' logos also invariably appears in publications – in bilateral, trilateral or quadrilateral form, as appropriate. The DRCF's outputs commonly provide a carefully worded introductory explanation of how the forum has been set up.

Our inquiry suggests that at an operational level the staff often see as cumbersome the need to refer each piece of work for clearance by the collaborating regulators, although its necessity is acknowledged. We have been told of hold-ups while acceptable wording is negotiated between contributing agencies prior to sign-off. The members' different IT systems also require added

effort for cooperation to work smoothly across organisational boundaries. Diverse regimes of confidentiality observed by the four regulators are also described as impacting on the flow of information during cross-regulator cooperation.

A striking outcome of the neo-regulatory model embodied in the DRCF is that it is seen by staff at different levels as providing career-enhancing opportunities because it enlarges the skillset and range of expertise of those who work for it. Staff describe themselves as becoming more effective generalists due to their regular cross-regulator work. Bilateral cooperation is particularly highly valued for the depth of engagement it engenders. We have been told that working for the DRCF may enhance promotion prospects. The DRCF's small core team provides anchorage in a system mainly characterised by time-limited engagements to work on specific projects amidst a wider culture of regular staff turnover. The DRCF's organisational architecture, with its personnel ultimately based in one or other of the quartet, limits longer-term career identification with the DRCF project. Strikingly, veterans aside, few members of the DRCF offer a well-informed account of its origins.

The following list indicates a possible taxonomy of activities, based on the preliminary analysis of our interviews and the DRCF's published outputs.

1. Think tank (emerging issues, competence coordination, policy influence)
2. Capacity building (training, secondments, information systems)
3. Guidance to regulators and regulatees (articulating cross-regulatory understanding and regulatory boundaries on critical issues; negotiating common understanding of new powers)
4. Coordination on concrete regulatory interventions or enforcement (concurrent legal underpinnings)
5. Service for regulatees (advice on cross-regulatory queries for firms, expert publics)
6. International network (convening powers)
7. Governance (annual reports, work plans, terms of reference)

Each of these activities appears to offer value added. A question to be explored more fully, particularly in terms of brokerage, is their distinct contribution.

The DRCF's future

The UK government's present rethinking of the British state's positioning in a globally contested regulatory firmament may well impact on regulators' strategies. Changing conditions affecting the quartet might have knock-on effects on the DRCF. Legal research has shown that, over time,

concurrent regulatory practices shift in line with legislative change and the political and economic winds that drive these.

Given its underlying conditions of existence, we have considered whether the DRCF's status as a brokerage agent offers the prospect of longer-term durability. We are not alone in posing this question: it was articulated, without prompting, during some of our interviews.

Along with questions about how regulation of digital platforms will be conducted in coming years, the scope of AI regulation is also moot. The DRCF is party to the national conversation on AI, notably in respect of its work on algorithms. If a dedicated AI regulator were to be established, might this become part of the DRCF, in a strategic expansion of the forum's scope?

From a quite different perspective, the DRCF's Terms of Reference – in effect, its constitution – do make it vulnerable to changing circumstances. If, for instance, a member regulator was to withdraw from the present arrangement, would the DRCF's future be sustainable?

However, it is important to underline that even if the DRCF's present configuration were to change, to date the UK has been at the forefront of stress-testing a think tank/brokerage model that is open to further development for cross-regulatory action in the digital sphere and AI.

Arguably, a flexible, risk-based and innovation-focused approach to regulation needs foresight and coordination. The invention of the DRCF as a neo-regulatory model appears to be a timely response to fast moving digital technology, global platform firms' strategies and far-reaching geopolitical shifts.

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